

AZERBAIJANI MUGHAMS IN NIZAMI GANJAVI'S WORK AS EXEMPLARY EXAMPLES OF NATIONAL-SPIRITUAL VALUES AND AESTHETIC EDUCATION

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Abstract

The article has been dedicated to the commentary of mugams in Nizami Gancavi's creation. It has been commented on here giving an explanation Nizami Gancavi's mugams as national moral values. It is shown in the article that, Nizami Gancavi considers Azerbaijan mugams as both national-moral values and the school of the strangest aesthetic artistic taste bringing up. The article reflects both etymological shade of meaning and dedicating of them to which historical and political events. The article gives information about the history of musical instruments which are used during performance mugam sets-as ney, tar, saz, dutar, chegane, drum, horn, fagana, oud, setar, rubab, barbed, jang, arganum, rud, daf, etc.

Keywords: national-spiritual values, moral, aesthetic values, mugham, tar

As is known, Azerbaijani mughams are considered one of the oldest and richest national and spiritual values of our nation. These national-spiritual values ensure the spiritual richness of the growing generation and serve to shape their aesthetic-artistic tastes. In fact, each of the national-spiritual values pleases people's taste and has a strong influence on the formation of their aesthetic-artistic tastes. Among them, mughams are of exceptional importance in this regard. Because Azerbaijani mughams are considered one of the richest national-spiritual values of the people, because both the words and the melody of these mughams not only form the national self-consciousness of the listeners, but also develop their aesthetic and artistic tastes. That is why our mughams are considered to be the first examples of aesthetic and artistic education. Of course, in the scientific literature, the formation of artistic perception, that is, aesthetics, separated from philosophy and sensory perception as an independent field of science, is mistakenly attributed to the name of the German philosopher Ernest Baumgarten who lived in XVIII century [1]. Considering that it was Al-Farabi who created the foundation of aesthetics, aesthetic feelings, aesthetic education, artistic taste, and the complex system of mugham tools. Then we must say that Nizami Ganjavi brought the artistic analysis of mugham dastgahs to "Khamasa" in XII century and included the formation of aesthetic-artistic taste education in his creativity. In order to determine the accuracy of the matter, if we pay close attention to how the great poet expertly separates the parallel lines between his philosophical judgments and artistic rites (emotional perception) in the poem "Khosrov and Shirin", we will clearly see that emotional perception (aesthetic sense) is not isolated from philosophical perception. If on the first side of these two lines there is the understanding of the world, the philosophical judgments spoken by Hormuzd, Shapur, Mahinbanu, Bahram, Farhad, Maryam, Shiruyya, then on the second side there is the exchange of famous mugham performers Barbad and Nikisa. This second line plays an unparalleled role in the development of the creative ability and aesthetic taste of the artistic thinking of the young generation [5, p.89].

Generally speaking, in his poem "Khosrov and Shirin", Nizami Ganjavi describes the mugham dastgahs, their colors, endings, preludes, classifications, branches and corners played by two prominent mugham masters, whom he invited to the eish-ishrat majlis he organized for Bahram Shah, with such great mastery that during the period, Azerbaijani mugham dastgahs spent their formative period [2].

Nizami Ganjavi, who expertly describes the period of formation of Azerbaijani mugam instruments, draws our mugams to the analysis both as national and spiritual values and as the most powerful aesthetic and artistic educational tool. In Nizami Ganjavi's analysis, famous mugham performers named Barbad and Nikisa, who were invited to the Eish-ishrat party, face each other and have a kind of competition. Each of them skillfully presents thirty of the hundred samples they know from Azerbaijani mugham dastgahs [3].

In Nizami's work, Barbadi talks about a hundred musical examples that he knows perfectly. In fact, these examples are considered the richest artistic treasure of our nation. The poet's extensive discussion of thirty of these hundred songs and his masterful interpretation of their aesthetic, philosophical, and artistic values allow us to reveal another aspect of Nizami's genius. In fact, those thirty songs should be understood as the initial foundation of the classifications, colors, and derivations that are considered to be the constituent parts of our mughams today [5, p.90]. To be more precise, we should say that Nizami gives the mugham branches, classifications and results performed by Barbad or Nikisa as the components of the most leading mughams. Because in Nizami's depictions, talking about the performance of leading mughams such as "Rast", "Shur", "Rahab", "Bayati-Shiraz", "Segah" in the scenes of Barbad's exchange with Nikisa should be understood as an expression of deep love for mughams at that time [4].

In Nizami Ganjavi's poem "Khosrov and Shirin", in the background of the exchange of Barbad and Nikisa, mughams and the color, classification, daramad, which are considered important components in their performance, and the musical instruments considered necessary in the performance of introductions (drums,

trumpets, fagana - chogana, oud, setar, saz, rubab, barbad, jang, arganun - kanon, rud, etc.), skillfully talks about the possibilities of performance. It is true that it is possible to find information about those musical instruments in some sources, albeit superficially, before Nizami. For example, the ancient Greek historian Herodotus (V century BC) in his book "History" talks about the attack of the troops of Tomiris, originally from the Azeri-Oghuz tribes, leading the Persian (Persian) troops, to the sound of drums and trumpets.

Or Istekhri, an Arab geographer who lived in IX-X centuries, mentions only the names of Azerbaijani musical instruments: horn, trumpet, kus (percussion instrument) and oud. This shows that Nizami Ganjavi gave detailed and systematic information about the musical instruments that existed in ancient times and their performance possibilities. In the section "Praise of Chalgichi Barbadin" of the poem "Khosrov and Shirin", the poet described the great talent of the Azerbaijani people in the example of Barbad in rich, poetic language [5, p.91].

In the work, the fact that the prominent mugham player Nikisa completed the classification he started on "Rast" with "Rast" mugham, and Barbed started playing with "Shur" mugham are skillfully written by Nizami of these two ancient mughams because at that time, either "Rast" or Great respect and love for "Shur" mughams, listening to them with perfect aesthetic-artistic taste arose from the requirements of that time.

Barbad also sings thirty songs he chooses from a hundred songs he knows on his favorite barbad (a stringed musical instrument). Barbad opens this beautiful assembly organized in the presence of Khosrov with "Ganji-badavard". The dictionary meaning of the word "Ganji-Badavard" means "treasure that comes with the wind". It can be assumed that Nizami used this expression as an allegory. Because the poet uses the expression "Ganji-badavard" in the earlier chapters of the work:

Shapur stood alone before the throne,

The treasurer of "Ganji-Badavardin" is alone.

From this, we can conclude that in order to make the artistic value of a musical piece more valuable, even before Nizami, they likened it to a "treasure that came with the wind". It is interesting that this sad and lyrical mugham lived in the spiritual memory of the Daramadi people for a long time and has reached our times [5, p.91]. In the last verse described by Nizami, the word "ganj" (which is now the root of the word Ganja. M.C) is understood as "treasure", and the word "averd" as "coming, bringing". Nizami seems to want to say that as much as the treasure that comes from the wind created by God, the rich wind, the branch of "Shur" called "Ganji-Badavard" was considered as much a valuable treasure for Shapur. Because the "Shuri-Nava" branch of the "Shur" instrument has such a strong influence that it is performed at such a high level with the singer's pleasant voice, mugham skills, and artistic taste experience that the listener is momentarily surprised by the pleasure he gets from the very precious treasure that comes with his hand and feels superior to desire and love.

It is no coincidence that the two great geniuses of our nation: Mir Mohsen Navvab and Uzeyir Hajibeyov, have extensively analyzed the position of "Sabz-der-Sabz" and "Sazi-Nowruz" music samples in the mugham genre in their works. The greatest music researcher of XIX century, Mir Mohsen Navvab Karabagi (Shushinski), systematized Azerbaijani mughams under 12 dastgahs, including 24 branches, 48 corners, and 15 avazats. Among them, "Sabz-dar-sabz" is included in that system as a corner or in "Khosrov and Shirin" From this, it can be concluded that either the "Sabz-dar-Sabz" mugham branch or the "Sazi-Nowruz" mugham sample was performed more widely in different periods when Islamic values were circulating, and their performance opportunities were enriched. The enrichment of these changes in accordance with the respect of Islamic values should not be forgotten. One can see a very magnificent educational school of the mugham departments and corners described by Nizami, either in the melody or the words. In this educational school, in addition to aesthetic taste and artistic talent, spiritual and moral qualities such as patriotism, friendship, companionship, brotherhood, sincerity, kindness, cleanliness form a unity. In the twelfth century, Nizami's artistic assessment of our mughams became relevant for all subsequent centuries and has been able to maintain its relevance even today.

Nizami Ganjavi, in addition to evaluating the artistic and aesthetic value of our mughams, which are an irreplaceable school of education, also connects the history of their creation, emotional influence, the formation of any branch and corner with certain historical events [5, p.93].

As it is known, "Chahargah" mugham reflects moral qualities such as bravery, combativeness, determination to win. In the past, those who performed this mugham benefited from examples of artistic creativity that reflected the spirit of struggle, determination to win, invincibility, and hatred for the enemy. Nizami Ganjavi also points to any historical events by recalling such nuances in his work.

Nizami, on the one hand, shows that mughams evoke in the listener feelings of fear, heroism, bravery, determination to win, struggle, in addition to the feeling of love and beauty, on the other hand, he recalls a historical event in the Shahnameh. Sayavush is the name of one of the main copies in the Shahnameh. He is the son of Keikavus, the king of Iran. The Turanian king Afrasiyab beheaded (executed) Sayavush, and Keikavus joined forces with the legendary Rustam Zal to avenge his son and declared war against Afrasiyab as "Kini-Sayavush". So, according to Nizami, listening to each mugham branch and enjoying its artistic rites, it is necessary to deeply understand the historical and philosophical essence of the example related to life events [5, p. 93].

Apparently, Nizami considers mughams to be the richest of national and spiritual values. If the words reflected in this wealth reflect the historical events that give the listener a scientific worldview, the melodiousness, melodiousness, melodiousness, artistic ability, unique elements of taste, in short, the strong aesthetic-impressive power of the melody takes the listener to a

completely unusual world. In this extraordinary world, every person who listens to mugham is enriched by the influence of the melody of the mugham, as much as he benefits from the wisdom of the words.

Generally speaking, if Nizami Ganjavi's attitude towards music, mugham, mugham instruments, departments, results, and classifications of these instruments creates information about the richest pearls of Azerbaijani musical culture in the reader and listener, valuable sayings of philosophical essence in the words of mughams enrich their worldviews. Familiar with the examples of musical culture such as musical instruments involved in mugham performance, including ney, tar, saz, dutar, chegane, tambourine, trumpet, fagana - chogana, oud, setar, rubab, barbed, jang, arganun

- canon, rud, tambourine. Readers and listeners can get detailed information about very rare musical instruments.

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